

Determination of Nitrates in Water using a New Spectrophotometric Method

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A new and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrate in water is described. Nitrate is reduced to nitrite with zinc dust in an ammoniacal medium in presence of manganous chloride. The nitrite is used to diazotise *p*-aminoacetophenone for subsequent coupling with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine to form a purple coloured dye. The dye has an absorption maxima at 545 nm and Beer's law is obeyed over a concentration 0.1–0.8 ppm nitrate. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of nitrate in various polluted water samples.

NITRATES are regarded as major water pollutants and represent the most completely oxidised state of nitrogen commonly found in water^{1,2}. The common methods for the determination of nitrates are based on nitration of phenols³, chromotropic acid^{1,4} and that based on Griess type reaction⁵. Various other methods are also reported⁶.

In the present communication nitrate is determined by reducing to nitrite by zinc dust and ammonia in presence of manganous chloride. The nitrite thus formed is used to diazotise *p*-aminoacetophenone (*p*-AAP) for subsequent coupling with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine (NEDA). *p*-AAP–NEDA reagent system has earlier been used for the determination of nitrites in water⁷. The absorbance of the purple coloured dye was measured at 545 nm.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss Spekol with 1 cm matched silica cells was used for all spectral measurements.

A stock solution of nitrate (1 mg ml⁻¹) prepared by dissolving sodium nitrate in demineralised water, working standards being prepared by appropriate dilution. A 1.2% ammonia solution was prepared in demineralised water. A 1% solution of manganous chloride tetrahydrate, 1% solution of *p*-aminoacetophenone in 1 : 4 HCl, and a 0.1% solution of *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine (NEDA) in demineralised water, 6M HCl and Zn dust were used. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure: To an aliquot of water sample (containing 2.5–20 μg of nitrate), ammonia solution (5 ml) and manganous solution (1 ml) were added and shaken thoroughly. To it zinc dust (0.2 g) was added and solution was shaken thoroughly. It was kept at 20° for 5 min. The solution was then filtered, *p*-AAP (1 ml) added and kept for 2 min for complete diazotisation. The acidity was maintained with 6M HCl (1 ml), then the NEDA solution (2 ml) added for coupling reaction

and kept for 20 min for full colour development. The volume was made up to the mark with 6M HCl and the absorbance measured at 545 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance of the purple coloured dye was measured at 545 nm against reagent blank.

Effect of varying reaction conditions :

Effect of temperature : A temperature range of 15–25° was found most suitable for the reduction. Increase in temperature reduces the reduction percentage. The method requires 5 min for reduction, 2 min for diazotisation and 20 min for complete colour development for optimum results ; increase in time shows no adverse effect. Ammonia solution (5 ml), manganous solution (1 ml) and zinc dust (0.2 g) were required for ~96% reduction. The optimum pH of the solution was ~10–11, and at low pH, decrease in percentage of reduction was noticed. pH 2–3 was required for diazotisation/coupling reaction. The purple coloured dye was found to be stable for 24 h.

Beer's law, Sandell's sensitivity and reproducibility: Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 2.5–20 μg/25 ml of nitrate (0.1–0.8 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be 5.73 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.001 μg cm⁻² respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing water sample containing 10 μg/25 ml of nitrate for a period of 10 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ±0.0043 and ±1.18% respectively.

Reduction ratio of nitrate to nitrite : Of the various reducing agents studied like hydrazine⁸, zinc dust⁹, zinc–ammonia¹⁰ and zinc–ammonia in presence of manganous¹¹, the latter was chosen for reduction, since it showed best results. This method reports 100% reduction, but even after

repeated analysis only ~96% reduction could be achieved.

Effect of foreign species: Effect of various co-pollutants were studied to assess the validity of the method. Known amounts of co-pollutants were added to solutions containing 10 µg nitrate/25 ml prior to analysis, and then the solution was analysed by the reported method. The tolerance limit for different ions is given in Table 1.

(Table 2 contd.)

Pond water ^a	—	4.86	4.82
	—	7.30	7.20
	—	12.20	12.30
	—	15.14	15.14
	—	20.30	20.10
River water ^a	—	3.90	3.80
	—	7.90	7.60
	—	19.05	19.00
	—	30.50	31.00
	—		

^aMean of three replicate analysis.

^bSamples were collected from different points.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN SPECIES

Species	Tolerance limit ^a µg
CuII ^a	250
CrIV	400
FeIII ^b , Phenol	1 000
CdII ^a , NiII ^a , Formaldehyde	1 200
PbII ^a , MnII ^a , CaII ^a , SnII ^a	1 250
SrII ^a	1 800
Aniline	2 400
BeII, LiI, SbIII, BiIII ^b , SeIV, Fluoride, Bromide	2 500
Phosphate, Cyanide	5 000
Sulphate	20 000

^aVariation = ± 2%.

^bMasked with 1 ml of 0.01 M EDTA.

^cMasked with 1 ml of 10% sodium potassium tartrate.

Application: To check the validity of the method, water samples from nearby tank, pond and Kharoon river were analysed for nitrate. Kharoon river water receives effluents from a nearby fertiliser factory and a steel factory. Tap water was also analysed by preparing synthetic samples because of the absence of nitrate in tap water. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—APPLICATION OF METHOD FOR ANALYSIS OF WASTE WATER

Sample	Amount of nitrate added µg	Amount found ^a (µg)	
		Present method	Phenol disulphonic acid method
Tap water	2.50	2.45	2.50
	5.00	4.90	4.80
	7.50	7.35	7.20
	12.50	12.12	11.87
Tank water ^a	—	2.50	2.40
	—	3.20	3.15
	—	3.70	3.65
	—	4.30	4.10

The proposed method was compared with the known methods^{1,6,8-10,12} and found to be more advantageous due to faster and high percentage of reduction of nitrates to nitrites.

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